

doi:10.5281/zenodo.15068935

Demographic Variables As Predictors Of Antisocial Personality Disorder (APD) Among Adolescents: Counselling Implications

¹Amaechi-Udogu, Vivian Chukwunonyenim (Ph.D) & ²Isukwem Gideon Chidozie (Ph.D)

Department of Educational Psychology, Guidance and Counselling
Faculty of Education,
University of Port Harcourt, Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria

¹Email: vivian.amaechi-udogu@uniport.edu.ng

²Email: davegide94@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The study investigated demographic variables as predictors of antisocial personality disorder among secondary school adolescents. The study adopted the ex-post-facto research design. The population of the study comprised all 14,784 senior secondary school students in the 16 public secondary schools in Obio/Akpor LGA of Rivers State. The study used a sample of 180 students who were independently selected using purposive sampling technique. Two self-developed instruments titled 'Demographic Inventory and Antisocial Personality Disorder Scale were used to collect data for the study. The reliability of the instruments was determined using the Cronbach Alpha method of internal consistency, therefore the coefficients obtained were Demographic Inventory 0.71, Antisocial Personality Disorder Scale 0.84 respectively. The study was guided by four research questions as well as four corresponding hypotheses. The data was analyzed with mean, standard deviation and independent sample t-test. The findings of the study revealed that, gender, family type and socioeconomic status significantly predicted antisocial personality disorder (APD) among secondary school adolescents, while location did not. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended among others that counseling for adolescents with antisocial personality disorder (APD) should be encouraged in schools with the aim of improving students' social skills and interpersonal relationships. Moreover, teachers should pay greater attention to students both in the classroom and at the playground so as to identify students with antisocial personality disorder (APD) and refer such students to the school counsellor for remediation.

Keywords: adolescents, antisocial personality disorder, students, secondary school

INTRODUCTION

Antisocial personality disorder (APD), also known as dissocial personality disorder, is characterized by a pervasive and persistent disregard for morals, social norms, emotional and physical rights and feelings of others. (American Psychiatric Association, 2000). It is a psychological condition in which a person exhibits a long-term pattern of manipulating, exploiting, or violating the rights of others without any remorse. Mayo-Clinic (2016) defined antisocial personality disorder (APD) as a mental condition in which a person consistently shows no regard for right and wrong and ignores the rights and feelings of

others. Individuals with this personality disorder typically have no regret in exploiting others in harmful ways for their own gain or pleasure, and frequently manipulate and deceive other people through wit and a facade of superficial charm or through intimidation and violence (Compton, Conway, Stinson, Colliver, & Grant, 2005). They may display arrogance, think lowly and negatively of others, and lack remorse for their harmful actions and have a callous attitude to those they have harmed (Berger, 201; Widiger & Corbitt, 1995). Hare (1993), observed that individuals with antisocial personality disorder usually act with complete lack of conscience and empathy, they selfishly take what they want and do as they please, violating social norms and expectations without the slightest sense of guilt or regret.

David (2001) stressed that individuals with antisocial personality disorder are often impulsive and reckless, failing to consider or disregarding the consequences of their actions. They may repeatedly disregard and jeopardize their own safety and the safety of others and place themselves and others in danger. They are often aggressive, hostile and display a dysregulated temper and can lash out violently with provocation or frustration (National Institute of Health and Care Excellence, (NICE), 2013). Sequel to this, Poju (2002) maintained that violence and aggressive behaviours among children are signs of antisocial personality disorder which is often missed or disregarded as a passing phase in their developmental stages. He further explained that such behaviours are carried on into adolescence and adulthood. These behaviours may cause problems in relationships or at school and its often criminal. Adolescents with antisocial personality disorder usually have problems establishing interpersonal relationships. Even when they have no problem in establishing relationships, they may have difficulties in sustaining and maintaining them. In recent times, there are different forms of antisocial behaviour exhibited by youths especially among secondary school adolescents in Rivers State. It is common to see secondary school adolescents bath one another with acid while quarreling over trivial matters. They act on impulse, lose their temper quickly, and lie easily and skillfully. They are often seen bullying other students, fighting, cheating, stealing, and destroying properties of their classmates and those of the school. Adolescents' antisocial personality disorder also takes the form of quarrelling, insubordination, vandalism, rule infractions, revolution, protest, rebellion and violation of social norms (Mayer, 2001). Studies have argued that some sociodemographic variables stand to predict antisocial personality disorder among secondary school adolescents. Therein, this study will examine demographic variables such as location, gender family type, and socio-economic status, as predictors of antisocial personality disorder among secondary school adolescents.

One variable that may predict antisocial personality disorder among adolescents is location. An individual's location can be classified as urban or rural. Ezike (1997) conceptualized urban location cosmopolitan town, city or neighborhood having increasing population with many social amenities. He further explained that rural location is a countryside, remote village or a geographical area that is located aside cities and towns, that is characterized by low population density fewer social amenities. The impact of location or place of residence as one of the contributory factors in the development of antisocial personality disorder among adolescents cannot be over-emphasized. Onukwufor (2013) observed that the geographic location or neighborhood in which a child resides may influence the child's personality. He further added that in a place where children are exposed to violence and aggressive behaviours in the form of robbery, kidnapping, rape and even murder, the resultant effect is antisocial personality disorder. Berger (2003) maintained that urban dwellers have diverse cultural and ethnic backgrounds which tend make them more individualistic and often show less concern for the plight of others compared to rural areas. Olseh (2010) also stressed that adolescents in urban areas may seem to have higher level of exposure to violence, substance use and abuse, perhaps due to accessibility of information technology, social media, and news and entertainment media, which makes them more susceptible to antisocial personality disorder. However, Spencer and Bryant (2000) observed that adolescents in rural areas are at greater risk for participating developing antisocial personality disorder than adolescents in urban areas. Wachikwu and Ibegbunam (2012) stressed that children raised in aversive and punitive environments are usually verbally abused, spanked and sometimes injuries are inflicted on them for any perceived

misconduct (real or imagined), and this negatively affects children and leads to antisocial personality disorder (APD).

Gender has been implicated as a factor predicting antisocial personality disorder among adolescents. Gender is the range of physical, biological, mental and behavioural characteristics pertaining to and differentiating between masculinity and femininity (Haig, 2004). Depending on the context, the term may refer to biological sex (i.e. the state of being male, female), sex based social structure (including gender roles and other social roles) or gender identity (Udry, 2004). Nwanneka and Joseph (2015) observed that boys by their very nature exhibit more physical, verbal aggression and thuggery while antisocial behaviours in girls is more subtle, indirect and relational involving harmful manipulation of others. They further suggested that antisocial personality disorder is more common with male adolescents than female. Antisocial personality disorder was diagnosed in approximately 3% of male and 1% of female adolescent in the United State of America (American Psychiatric Associate, 1998). American Psychiatric Association (1998) also asserted that the incident of antisocial personality disorder appeared to have increased in USA over the preceding decade and might be as high as 6 to 16% in males under 18 years and 2 to 9% in females under 18 years. Manie (1998) also reported that the likelihood of boys to develop antisocial personality disorder was four to eight times greater than for girls. Also, Kazdin cited in Nwanneka and Joseph (2015) reported that antisocial personality disorder (APD) was more common among boys than girls.

The family is the most important primary group in the society and immediate social environment to which a child is developed and exposed (Adhiambo, Odwar and Mildred, 2011). A family is a bio-social group (Adani, 2001). It is primarily made up of father, mother and children. Notwithstanding, there are other types of families like nuclear, extended, stepparent family, single-parent, divorced or separated, intact, monogamous or polygamous families. A child learns to adjust to various situations of life according to the values and virtues provided by his or her family. In nuclear families, we have the father, mother and children. In extended families, there exists a much wider kinship network, of which the primary family is only a very small part. An extended family includes grandparents and grandchildren, aunts and uncles, nieces, nephews, cousins, and even more (Lewis, 2006). Children grow up in families which provide consistent and relatively permanent relationship which affects their behaviour both positively and negatively (Dudley, 2012). Muntreal (1991) stressed that children from small size or nuclear family less aggressive and antisocial than those from large size or extended family. Felson and Tedeschi (1993) observed that children from extended families are frequently exposed to hostile people and violent behaviours and this increases the likelihood of developing antisocial personality disorder (APD). They further explained that children from such family usually have to contend with intense emotions such as frustration, loneliness, feelings of anger, thus they expel some of those emotions on other people without feeling remorse. Gasa (2005) also observed that the highest rates of antisocial personality disorder (APD) are found in families where aggressive models abound and where antisocial behavior is regarded as high valued attribute.

Socio-economic status is a way of looking at how individuals or families fit into society using economic and social measures that have been shown to impacts individuals' health and well-being. It is the grouping of people along occupational, educational and economic levels of the society (Santrock, 2004). Most problems associated with low socio-economic status are related to poverty. People of low socio-economic status often have less education and fewer economic resources (Lewbel, 2000). There are debates that the development of antisocial personality disorder (APD) among adolescents may be predicted by socio-economic status of parents. Some adolescents are nurtured in a state of abject poverty while some others are brought up in affluent conditions. For those brought up in affluent condition, life is good and there is no need to do anything that can endanger their lives. For those brought up in the poverty, the reverse is the case as they have to struggle for survival. Chauhan (1990) observed that poverty of parents makes it impossible for them to provide for their children and this give rise to frustration which ultimately trigger off anger and general antisocial behaviours in adolescents. Nwankwo

(2003) also noted that children born into impoverished environments might take to socially unacceptable behaviours such as stealing, fighting, bullying, as survival strategy.

Antisocial personality disorder negatively affects adolescents' social, emotional and academic success. It leads to poor social and interactive skills, often resulting unstable interpersonal relationships. Some psychological effects of antisocial personality disorder include detachment from family and friends, depression, loneliness, low self-esteem, irritability, mood swings, feelings of social rejection and frustration. Adolescents' antisocial personality disorder often lead to failure to conform to social norms, aggressiveness, drug abuse and substance dependence, violation of the rights and feelings of others, lower academic achievement, and school drop-outs. It is in view of these, that the researcher is motivated to examine demographic variables as predictors of antisocial personality disorder (APD) among secondary school adolescents.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is to examine demographic variables as predictors of antisocial personality disorder (APD) among secondary school adolescents in Rivers State. Specifically, the study intends to achieve the following;

1. Determine the extent to which location predicts antisocial personality disorder (APD) among secondary school adolescents in Rivers State.
2. Determine whether gender predicts antisocial personality disorder (APD) among secondary school adolescents in Rivers State.
3. Find out the extent to which family types (nuclear/extended) predicts antisocial personality disorder (APD) among secondary school adolescents in Rivers State.
4. Ascertain the extent to which socioeconomic status predicts antisocial personality disorder (APD) among secondary school adolescents in Rivers State.

Research Questions

1. To what extent does location predict antisocial personality disorder (APD) among secondary school adolescents in Rivers State?
2. How does gender predict antisocial personality disorder (APD) among secondary school adolescents in Rivers State?
3. To what extent does family types (nuclear/extended) predicts antisocial personality disorder (APD) among secondary school adolescents in Rivers State?
4. To what extent does socioeconomic status predict antisocial personality disorder (APD) among secondary school adolescents in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

1. Location (Rural/Urban) does not significantly predict antisocial personality disorder (APD) among secondary school adolescents in Rivers State.
2. Gender (male/female) does not predict antisocial personality disorder (APD) among secondary school adolescents in Rivers State.
3. Family types (nuclear/extended) does not significantly predict antisocial personality disorder (APD) among secondary school adolescents in Rivers State.
4. Socioeconomic status (high/low) does not significantly predict antisocial personality disorder (APD) among secondary school adolescents in Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted the ex-post-facto research design. The population of the study comprised all 14,784 senior secondary school students in the 16 public secondary schools in Obio/Akpor LGA of Rivers State. The study used a sample of 180 students who were independently selected using purposive sampling technique. Two self-developed instruments (questionnaire) titled 'Demographic Inventory and Antisocial Personality Disorder Scale were used to collect data for the study. The reliability of the instruments was

determined using the Cronbach Alpha method of internal consistency, therefore the coefficients obtained were Sociodemographic Inventory 0.71, Antisocial Personality Disorder Scale 0.84 respectively. Mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions, while independent t-test analysis was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

The data was analyzed with mean, standard deviation and independent sample t-test statistics at 0.05 significant level.

Research Question 1: *To what extent does location predict antisocial personality disorder (APD) among secondary school adolescents in Rivers State?*

Hypothesis 1: Location (Rural/Urban) does not significantly predict antisocial personality disorder (APD) among secondary school adolescents in Rivers State.

Table 1: Showing t-test analysis on the prediction of location on antisocial personality disorder (APD)

Location	N	\bar{X}	Std.Dev.	Crti-t	Cal-t	Df	P
Rural	91	37.42	4.83	1.96	0.343	178	0.732
Urban	89	37.24	4.60				

The data analyzed shows that the rural and urban students are numbered 91 and 89 respectively. The rural student had the mean score of 37.42 and SD of 4.83. On the other hand, urban students had the mean score of 37.24 and a standard deviation of 4.60. Based on their mean scores it is deduced that rural students tend to have antisocial personality disorder more than the urban students by a mean difference of 0.19. However, when these mean difference was subjected to an independent t-test, a calculated t-value of 0.343 was obtained at a degree of freedom of 1.96 at 0.732 significant level. Thus since the p-value of 0.732 is greater than 0.05, the chosen level of probability it is decided that location had insignificant prediction on antisocial personality disorder (APD) among secondary school adolescents.

Research Question 2: *How does gender predict antisocial personality disorder (APD) among secondary school adolescents in Rivers State?*

Hypothesis 2: Gender (male/female) does not predict antisocial personality disorder (APD) among secondary school adolescents in Rivers State.

Table 2: Showing t-test analysis on the prediction of gender on antisocial personality disorder (APD)

Gender	N	\bar{X}	Std.Dev	Crti-t	Cal-t	Df	P
Male	94	34.15	3.40	1.96	10.067	178	S
Female	86	29.13	4.57				

The result of data analyzed showed that male \bar{X} =35.15, SD=3.40, female had \bar{X} =29.13, SD=4.57, with a cal. t. of 10.067, df =178, crit. t. =1.96. Since cal. t is higher than the crit. t. it therefore means that the null hypothesis is rejected. Meaning, gender significantly predict antisocial personality disorder (APD) among secondary school adolescents. Further analysis of the result shows that antisocial personality disorder (APD) tends to be high in male than female.

Research Question 3: *To what extent does family types (nuclear/extended) predicts antisocial personality disorder (APD) among secondary school adolescents in Rivers State?*

Hypothesis 3: family type (nuclear/extended) does not significantly predict antisocial personality disorder (APD) among secondary school adolescents in Rivers State

Table 3: Showing t-test analysis on the prediction of family type on antisocial personality disorder (APD)

Family Type	N	\bar{X}	Std.Dev	Crti-t	Cal-t	Df	P
Nuclear	89	30.28	5.07	1.96	5.765	178	S
Extended	91	34.24	4.09				

The result of data analyzed showed that nuclear family had \bar{X} =30.28, SD=5.07, extended family \bar{X} =34.24, SD=4.09, with a cal. t. of 5.765, df =178, crit. t. =1.96. Since cal. t is higher than the crit. t. it therefore means that the null hypothesis is rejected. Meaning that, nuclear and extended family significantly predict antisocial personality disorder (APD) among secondary school adolescents. The data also indicated that extended family type tend to predict antisocial personality disorder (APD) among secondary school adolescents more compared to nuclear family type.

Research Question 4: *To what extent does socioeconomic status predict antisocial personality disorder (APD) among secondary school adolescents in Rivers State?*

Hypothesis 4: Socioeconomic status (high/low) does not significantly predict antisocial personality disorder (APD) among secondary school adolescents in Rivers State.

Table 4: Showing t-test analysis on the prediction of socioeconomic status on antisocial personality disorder (APD)

SES	N	\bar{X}	Std.Dev	Crti-t	Cal-t	Df	P
High	89	34.52	4.09	1.96	6.623	178	S
Low	91	30.08	4.85				

The result of data analyzed showed that high SES \bar{X} =34.52, SD=4.09, low SES family had \bar{X} =30.08, SD=4.85, with a cal. t. of 10.067, df =178, crit. t. =1.96. Since cal. t is higher than the crit. t. It therefore means that the null hypothesis is rejected and that, high/ low SES of parents predicts antisocial personality disorder (APD) among secondary school adolescents. Further analysis of the result shows that low SES tends to predict antisocial personality disorder (APD) more than high SES.

RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Location and Antisocial Personality Disorder (APD)

The result analyzed showed that location does not significantly predict antisocial personality disorder (APD) among secondary school adolescents in Rivers State. The null was retained. This however implies that location factor does not predispose or preclude anyone to/from the development of antisocial personality disorder (APD). The findings of this study however disagrees with an earlier study by Berger (2003) who found out that urban dwellers have diverse cultural and ethnic backgrounds which tend make them more individualistic and often show less concern for the plight of others compared to rural areas. Olseh (2010) also found out that adolescents in urban areas may seem to have higher level of exposure to violence, substance use and abuse, perhaps due to accessibility of information technology, social media, and news and entertainment media, which makes them more susceptible to antisocial personality disorder.

Gender and Antisocial Personality Disorder (APD)

The finding of the study revealed that gender significantly predict antisocial personality disorder (APD) among secondary school adolescents in Rivers State. Hence, the null hypothesis was rejected. Further analysis of the result shows that antisocial personality disorder (APD) tends to be high in male than female. The result of this study is in agreement with an earlier study by Nwanneka and Joseph (2015) found out that antisocial personality disorder is more common with male adolescents than female. American Psychiatric Association (1998) also found out that antisocial personality disorder was diagnosed in approximately 3% of male and 1% of female adolescent in the United State of America.

Family Type and Antisocial Personality Disorder (APD)

The finding of the study revealed that nuclear and extended family significantly predict antisocial personality disorder (APD) among secondary school adolescents. The null hypothesis was rejected. Furthermore, the finding showed that extended family type tends to predict antisocial personality disorder (APD) among secondary school adolescents more compared to nuclear family type. The findings of this study is in agreement with the study by Muntreal (1991) who found out that children from small size or nuclear family less aggressive and antisocial than those from large size or extended family. Felson and Tedeschi (1993) also found out that children from extended families are frequently exposed to hostile people and violent behaviours and this increases the likelihood of developing antisocial personality disorder (APD).

Socioeconomic Status and Antisocial Personality Disorder (APD)

The result of the study showed that socioeconomic status significantly predicts antisocial personality disorder (APD) among secondary school adolescents in Rivers State. The null hypothesis was rejected. Further analysis of the result also revealed that low socioeconomic status tends to predict antisocial personality disorder (APD) more than high socioeconomic status. The findings of this study agrees with an earlier study by Chauhan (1990) found out that poverty of parents makes it impossible for them to provide for their children and this give rise to frustration which ultimately trigger off anger and general antisocial behaviours in adolescents. Nwankwo (2003) also found out that children born into impoverished environments might take to socially unacceptable behaviours such as stealing, fighting, bullying, as survival strategy.

CONCLUSION

Antisocial personality disorder (APD), is characterized by a pervasive and persistent disregard for morals, social norms, emotional and physical rights and feelings of others. It is a psychological condition in which a person exhibits a long-term pattern of manipulating, exploiting, or violating the rights of others without any remorse. Adolescents with this personality disorder typically have no regret in exploiting others in harmful ways for their own gain or pleasure, and frequently manipulate and deceive other people through wit and a facade of superficial charm or through intimidation and violence. They usually have problems establishing interpersonal relationships. Even when they have no problem in establishing relationships, they may have difficulties in sustaining and maintaining them. They act on impulse, lose their temper quickly, and lie easily and skillfully. Some psychological effects of antisocial personality disorder include detachment from family and friends, depression, loneliness, low self-esteem, irritability, mood swings, feelings of social rejection and frustration. Adolescents' antisocial personality disorder (APD) also leads to failure to conform to social norms, aggressiveness, drug abuse and substance dependence, violation of the rights and feelings of others. This study has shown that demographic variables such as gender, family type and socioeconomic status significantly predicts antisocial personality disorder (APD) among secondary school adolescents in Rivers State.

Counselling Implications

This study has the following counselling implications;

1. Counselling for adolescents with antisocial personality disorder (APD) should be encouraged in schools with the aim of improving students' social skills and interpersonal relationships.
2. School counsellors should pay greater attention to students both in the classroom and at the playground so as to identify students with antisocial personality disorder (APD) and offer prompt help to them.
3. Counsellors organize seminars and enlightenment programmes to sensitize parents, guardians and caregivers on the need to display love and affection to adolescents experiencing antisocial personality disorder (APD), as this will give them a sense purpose and belongingness, and change their behaviour of acting unkindly to others.

4. Counsellors should never be judgmental when dealing with adolescents experiencing antisocial personality disorder (APD), rather they should always displayed unconditional positive regard when helping them.

REFERENCES

- Adani, A. (2004). *Home environment as correlate of adjustment problem on secondary school adolescents in Benue State*. Unpublished M.Ed. Thesis, University of Nigeria, Nsukka.
- Adhiambo, M.W., Odwar, A.J. & Mildred, A.A. (2011). The relationship among school adjustment, gender, and academic achievement amongst secondary school students in Kisumu District Kenya. *Journal of Emerging Trends in Educational Research and Policy Studies* 2(6): 493-497.
- American Psychiatric Association (2000). *Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders. Fourth edition*. Washington, DC: Text revision.
- Berger, K. S. (2003). *The developing person through adulthood and adolescence*. England'. Worth Publishers.
- Compton WM, Conway KP, Stinson FS, Colliver J. D., & Grant, B. F. (2005). Prevalence, correlates, and comorbidity of DSM-IV antisocial personality syndromes and alcohol and specific drug use disorders in the United States: Results from the national epidemiologic survey on alcohol and related conditions. *Journal of Clinical Psychiatry*. 66 :677–685.
- David, M, (2001). *Personality and dangerousness : genealogies of antisocial personality disorder*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. ISBN 978-0521008754. OCLC 52493285.
- Dudley S. (2012) *Blended family kids benefit from time with grandparents*. Available from www.theblendedandstepfamilyresourcecenter.com.
- Ezike, B. U. (1997). *The effect of resource distribution and utilization on performance of students in chemistry*. M.Ed. Dissertation in University of Ibadan
- Felson, R. B., & Tedeschi, J. J. (1993). *Aggressive and violence social interactions perspectives*. Washington, DC. American Psychological Association.
- Gasa, V. G. (2005). *Learners' aggressive behaviour in secondary schools. A psycho-social perspective*. Unpublished Doctoral Dissertation, University of South Africa
- Lewbel, A., (2000). Semiparametric qualitative response model estimation with unknown heteroscedasticity or instrumental variables. *Journal of Econometrics* 97, 145–177.
- Lewis, J. (2006). *Family structure and stress family process*. 25, 235 – 247.
- Marie, (1998) Conduct disorder. *Society of special needs Adoptive Parents newsletter*. 14 (1).
- Mayer, G.R. (2001) *Antisocial behaviour: Its causes and prevention within our schools*. Retrieved from <http://www.accessmylibrary.com/article-IG-81565933/antisocial-behaviour-its-cause.html>.
- Mayo-Clinic (2016). *Overview: Antisocial personality disorder*.
- Muntreal, S.K. (1991). *Advanced educational psychology (2nd ed.)*. New Delhi. Rajteamal Electric Press.
- National Institute of Health and Care Excellence (2013). *Antisocial personality disorder: Prevention and management*. Retrieved from <http://www.nice.org.uk/guidance/cg77/chapters/introduction>
- Nwankwo, B.O. Nwoke, E. U., Chukwuocha, U. M., Obbany, A. O., Nwoga, K.C., Iwuagu, U.O., & Okereke C. (2010). Prevalence and predictor of Antisocial behaviour: A cross-sectional survey of adolescents in secondary schools in Owerri municipal, South-East, Nigeria. *Pakistan Journal of socio-sciences* 7(2)129-136
- Nwanneka, N., & Joseph, A. A. (2015) antisocial behaviours among Nigerian adolescents. *Journal of Research & Method in Education*, 5, (4) 31-36
- Onukwufor, J. N. (2013). Physical and verbal aggression among adolescent secondary school students in Rivers State of Nigeria. *International Journal of Education Learning and Development*,.1, (2), 73-84
- Santrock, J.W. (2004). *Child development*. (10th ed.). New York: McGraw Hill.
- Wachikwu, T. & Ibegbunam, J. O. (2012). Psychosocial factors influencing antisocial behaviour among secondary school students in Obio-Akpor Local Area of Rivers State. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 2 (1) 104-113